

Biomolecular structural studies using NMR : Re-emergence of an old idea[†]

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During recent years, the use of dipolar couplings has gained prominence in biomolecular structural studies particularly with the discovery and use of lyotropic liquid crystalline media with low molecular orders and appropriate solubility properties.

Though the idea of using dipolar couplings for such purposes has been there ever since the discovery of the technique of NMR spectroscopy of molecules oriented in liquid crystalline media nearly four decades back, practical difficulties such as the solubility and the spectral complexities in general have been responsible for such a long delay in actually exploiting the idea for biomolecular structural studies. During all these years attempts have been made by several active groups all over the world to overcome the difficulties, to use media with low order parameters and the discovery of new systems with desired solubility and the ordering properties. Such developments are discussed with emphasis on our own contributions and efforts in this emerging area of research.

Since the technique is now emerging as a very valuable and informative tool in biomolecular structural studies, a word of caution in interpreting such data in terms of molecular structure is also highlighted.

Proton Magnetic Resonance spectra of oriented systems become rapidly complex with the increase of number of interacting nuclei. This is because the spectra in most of the known thermotropic liquid crystals are usually strongly coupled. In addition, dipolar couplings between magnetically equivalent nuclei also influence the spectra and this adds to spectral complications. On the other hand, utility of the technique to structural studies particularly of complex systems is well recognized. Consequently, efforts have been made by several active groups all over the world to overcome such problems ever since the discovery of the method in 1963¹. The use of isotopic substitution followed by heteronuclear decoupling^{2,3}, multiple quantum spectroscopy⁴⁻⁷, near magic angle spinning^{8,9} and the use of liquid crystals with low order parameters^{10,11} are some of the attempts made in this direction. However, none of these techniques has been routinely employed due to practical difficulties.

During recent years, the technique has come into prominence with the discovery of low order lyotropic liquid crystals with appropriate solubility properties¹¹. The use of high magnetic fields for orienting solute molecules also promises a bright future¹². We have also been actively involved in such endeavours. During recent years, we have concentrated on the discovery of new thermotropic liquid crystals¹⁰ with low order parameters and proposed the use of natural abundance ²H-NMR spectroscopy¹³.

Major advances :

We concentrate on the three major directions of research in this area in the following sections : (a) the use of high magnetic fields for molecular orientation, (b) discovery of new thermotropic liquid crystals with low order parameters, and (c) the use of natural abundance ²H-NMR spectroscopy of oriented systems.

The use of high magnetic fields for molecular orientation : Molecules may be aligned by strong magnetic fields of the order of 10 T or above and the direct dipolar and the quadrupolar interactions may be observed as line-splitting. Such studies have the advantage that the orientational effects do not dominate the spectra with the result that the spectra are 'weakly' coupled and are, therefore, amenable to straightforward analysis procedures. The orientation is, in addition, achieved without the use of any external medium with the result that there are no solubility problems and the solvent-solute interactions are absent. With the availability of higher and higher magnetic field NMR spectrometers, this area may become extremely important in future. The higher the field, the greater is the orientation. The advances are likely to prove valuable particularly in biomolecular structural studies since the orientation information can be combined with the Nuclear Overhauser Effect (NOE) and the scalar coupling data for obtaining refined solution state structure. This was realized as early as 1990¹² and has been reiterated recently with the discovery

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of lyotropic liquid crystals with low molecular order¹¹. The use of magnetic field alignment (17.6 T) has been employed to study DNA¹⁴ and subsequently it has become one of the most active areas of research in biomolecular structural studies.

Discovery of thermotropic liquid crystals with low order parameters : Lyotropic liquid crystals with low order parameter have been used for structural studies of small molecules from 1967 onwards¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Their utility during recent years has been extended to large molecules with the discovery of new materials with appropriate properties¹¹. They, however, present solubility problems in general, the solutions are relatively difficult to prepare and the solvent-solute interactions become more prominent. Thermotropic liquid crystals, on the other hand promise new avenues to overcome some of the problems and provide alternatives. New liquid crystalline phases induced by addition of small amounts of non-mesogenic solutes to a quaternary ammonium salt, *N*-methyl-*N,N,N*-trioctadecylammonium iodide (MTA1) have recently been discovered¹¹. The low order parameter of the pure thermotropic nematic phase of the salt provides 'first' order spectra of the dissolved oriented molecules. The proton NMR spectrum of muconitrile in a normal conventional thermotropic liquid crystal is 'strongly' coupled and it is difficult to assign the lines to specific protons. However, the spectrum in MTA1 is 'weakly' coupled and straightforward to analyse. The order parameter is only about 3% of that of a normal thermotropic nematic phase consisting of rod-like molecules and is comparable to that for lyotropic nematic phases. As a result, MTA1 has potential for applications when 'first' order proton spectra of oriented molecules are needed.

The use of natural abundance ²H-NMR spectroscopy of oriented systems : The use of natural abundance ²H-NMR of molecules oriented in liquid crystal solvents as a practical tool has recently been suggested¹³. Typical spectra of molecules such as benzene and chloroform dissolved in normal thermotropic liquid crystals could be obtained in 20 hrs on an AMX-400 spectrometer. The technique has also been extended to a relatively complex case of *o*-dibromobenzene. The results demonstrate that the natural abundance ²H-NMR spectra of molecules dissolved in liquid crystals can be obtained within reasonable time on the present day spectrometers. The values of the order parameters thus obtained can help to analyze more complex proton spectra. Such experiments may enhance the scope of the technique of NMR spectroscopy of oriented molecules particularly when applying to more complicated systems.

Caution :

The studies described above demonstrate the recent advances in the field of NMR spectroscopy of oriented systems particularly as applied to complex biological systems. The main idea is to develop methodology either to reduce the spectra from normally 'strongly' coupled to 'weakly' coupled amenable to first order spectral analyses procedures or to get the orientational information from the simplified quadrupolar spectra and use it for analyzing the complex proton spectra. Though the 'weakly' coupled spectra are easy to analyze but the interpretation of the observed splitting in terms of the simple theoretical principles need a word of caution. The simplified version of the equation relating the dipolar couplings with the internuclear distances and the order parameters usually assumes that the average order parameter and the $\langle 1/r^3 \rangle$ are not interdependent. Though it provides reasonable assumption in general for large orientations but serious discrepancies have been observed in some cases such as acetylene¹⁸, methanol¹⁹, tetramethylsilane¹⁹ to mention a few. The results in such cases have been interpreted in terms of more rigorous theories such as the multiple-site theory of orientation and other factors contributing to the splitting. This should serve as a caution for the determination of molecular structure from NMR studies of oriented systems particularly for molecules with low orientations. The results should, therefore, be verified by working under different conditions of orientation, e.g. by changing the solvent, concentration and/or temperature.

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